

IMAGE ANALYSIS MADE EASY: Using RootPainter to estimate coral surface area.

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This workshop will present the open-source and user-friendly machine learning tool ([RootPainter](#)), capable of estimating species surface area in remotely operated vehicle (ROV) video frames of the deep-sea. The original paper describing this tool can be found [here](#). The study that first demonstrated RootPainter's capabilities with marine images is available [here](#).

The workshop will take you through installation of the tool and the training process on a practise dataset (collected as part of the IceAGE3 project in 2020 by the ROV KIEL 6000) identifying *Primnoa* sp. Approximately 10 hours and 250 images are needed to develop a suitable model to identify *Primnoa* sp. Therefore, a pre-developed model for this species is also available for download at the end of the workshop. Users are invited to apply this model to the total dataset to see how information such as species surface area may be extracted from images.

The information regarding installation and model training included in this tutorial is also available in an interactive format within the [GoogleColab notebook](#). This tutorial uses GoogleColab for GPU access. If you wish to use a personal GPU (NVIDIA GPU with at least 8GB GPU memory required) or have access to an external GPU via your institution you should follow the 'server set-up' guide here: [GitHub](#).

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1. INSTALLATION

Installation is only described in this manual for Windows 11. Whilst the steps are the same, a video demonstrating installation on MacOS is available [here](#) if needed. There is also a video tutorial for installation on Windows 11 [here](#).

1.1 GoogleDrive

As we are utilising the free GPU from GoogleColab, RootPainter requires a way to synchronise files in a folder between the RootPainter application (client) and GoogleColab GPU (server). This can be done most easily on Mac and Windows through GoogleDrive but first requires GoogleDrive to be mapped to your device.

STEP 1: Ensure you have a Google account

If you have a @gmail email address then you already have a google account. We would recommend using your main email address to prevent confusion when syncing GoogleDrive files with your device. If you do not have a google account this must first be set-up: [create google account](#).

STEP 2: Download Google's 'drive for Desktop' software - [GoogleDrive download](#)

When installing you will be given some options. If you already have a large amount of data in GoogleDrive, you may prefer the streaming rather than mirror option to provide a faster setup. Streaming can result in slow image loading with RootPainter for larger images. If you experience this, you can mitigate it by right clicking the drive_rp_sync folder in GoogleDrive (in your local file system) and set 'Offline access' as 'Available Offline', which provides a substantial speedup.

Further troubleshooting for GoogleDrive for Desktop is available from google here: [troubleshooting](#).

1.2 Dataset Download

It is important to download the practise dataset at this stage so that it has time to sync with your GoogleDrive directory before continuing the workshop.

STEP 1: Download the dataset from the workshop shared drive: [Image Analysis Made Easy](#).

STEP 2: Ensure it is saved within your local GoogleDrive and available for offline access.

1.3 RootPainter

RootPainter can be downloaded and set-up through the interactive GoogleColab page. As this tutorial is for a marine image dataset, it will not be necessary to download the 'biopores dataset', where users can practise annotating holes in soil. Each line of code is accompanied by a description of its function. Pressing the play button next to the code will run it. We recommend using Google Chrome and logging in to your Google account **before** running the notebook.

STEP 1: Open the GoogleColab Set-up Notebook - [GoogleColab notebook](#)

The first section of text is information only. This provides more information about how the tool works, but the section in the red box is all that needs to be actioned.

RootPainterSetup - Colaboratory X +

https://colab.research.google.com/drive/104narYAvTbt-X4QEDrBSOZm_DRaAKHtA?usp=sharing#scrollTo=sbP09OrvRH12

RootPainterSetup ☆

File Edit View Insert Runtime Tools Help Changes will not be saved

+ Code + Text Copy to Drive

About RootPainter

RootPainter is a GUI-based software tool for the rapid training of deep neural networks for use in biological image analysis. RootPainter facilitates both fully-automatic and semi-automatic image segmentation. RootPainter uses a client server architecture and thus consists of a pair of programs (one on your computer, another on a server) that can, after an easy and user-friendly training process, identify and measure features in images. It has been tested with roots, root nodules, and biopores in soil. It could be trained to identify other kinds of features, such as leaves, bacterial colonies on agar plates and cancer cells.

RootPainter is open source, with all code available for download, inspection and modification from [this HTTPS URL](#).

Setup and run RootPainter with Google Colab

As many users do not have a powerful enough GPU installed on their computer, this guide will explain how to use RootPainter with a free GPU from google via their google colab service.

Credits

[Abraham George Smith](#) - Main author of this interactive tutorial and main developer of the RootPainter software.
[R. Ford Denison](#) - Testing, guidance on usability issues and collaboration with AGS on both the introductory and explanatory text.
[Eusun Han](#) - Testing and creation of the biopores dataset used in this tutorial.
[Silas Nyboe Orting](#) - Testing and the instructions for syncing on Linux.

Preliminary: Read paper

This will help you understand the related concepts, purpose and capabilities of RootPainter.
[RootPainter: Deep Learning Segmentation of Biological Images with Corrective Annotation](#)

Preliminary: Prepare Sync Software

RootPainter requires a way to synchronize files in a folder between the client and server if they aren't on the same machine. If you want to use a Google Colab GPU then you can use google drive's desktop app or rclone to do this.
Please see [RootPainter Sync Setup Guide](#)

Client-Server Architecture

RootPainter includes client and server components that interact with each other via file sync. The server can be ran in this notebook (using a GPU from google). Later on in this tutorial you will be instructed to download, install and run the client on your local computer.

Note: This web page is a type of web application called a jupyter notebook. Jupyter notebooks are open source web applications that allow you to write and run live code.

Note: I have written either 'Do every time' or 'First time only' to indicate if an instruction is something you only need to do once when first setting up the system or each time you want to run the RootPainter server.

Note: Once you have completed this setup you can re-run the server in the future by following the simplified instructions in the [Run RootPainter Server with colab](#) guide, which assumes you have already gone through this setup guide.

Note: Colab can be a bit slow. If you are using RootPainter for a very large project it might be better to get your own GPU.

Change runtime type. (First time only)

1. Select 'Runtime' in the top menu (of this notebook).
2. Select 'Change runtime type'
3. Select GPU (if it isn't already set as GPU)
4. Click SAVE

- Under the 'Runtime' tab, select 'Change runtime type'.

- Ensure that under 'Hardware accelerator' the 'GPU' option is selected.

STEP 2: Connect the GoogleColab Notebook with your GoogleDrive.

- Press the **play** button to run the code.

▾ Mount drive so data can be shared with client. (Do every time)

To run the following block of code. Hover your mouse over it and then click the play icon on the left of it.

Note: This may take you to another page where you need to authenticate with your google account.

If you find it takes ages (over three minutes) without doing anything then click the stop icon and then play again.

```

▶ from google.colab import drive
  drive.mount('/content/drive')

```

- Select **'Run anyway'** when the following warning message appears.

The screenshot shows a code cell with the following code: `from google.colab import drive` and `drive.mount('/content/drive')`. A warning dialog box is overlaid on the code cell. The dialog box has a title "Warning: This notebook was not authored by Google". The text inside the dialog box reads: "This notebook was authored by **abe@abesmith.co.uk**. It may request access to your data stored with Google, or read data and credentials from other sessions. Please review the source code before executing this notebook. Please contact the creator of this notebook at **abe@abesmith.co.uk** with any additional questions." At the bottom right of the dialog box, there are two buttons: "Cancel" and "Run anyway". The "Run anyway" button is highlighted with a red border.

- Select **'Connect to Google Drive'** in the next pop-up.

The screenshot shows the same code cell as above. A permission dialog box is overlaid on the code cell. The dialog box has a title "Permit this notebook to access your Google Drive files?". The text inside the dialog box reads: "This notebook is requesting access to your Google Drive files. Granting access to Google Drive will permit code executed in the notebook to modify files in your Google Drive. Make sure that you review the notebook code prior to allowing this access." At the bottom right of the dialog box, there are two buttons: "No, thanks" and "Connect to Google Drive". The "Connect to Google Drive" button is highlighted with a red border.

- Select your Google account.

The screenshot shows a "Sign in with Google" dialog box. The title is "Sign in with Google". Below the title is the Google logo. The main text reads: "Choose an account to continue to **Google Drive for desktop**". Below this text, there is a list of accounts. The first account is "Hannah Clark" with a blue profile picture icon. This account is highlighted with a red border. Below the list of accounts, there is a link "Use another account". At the bottom of the dialog box, there is a paragraph of text: "To continue, Google will share your name, email address, language preference, and profile picture with Google Drive for desktop. Before using this app, you can review Google Drive for desktop's [privacy policy](#) and [terms of service](#)."

- Allow GoogleDrive for desktop to access your Google Account.

Once the code has finished running a tick will appear next to the play button. The following code output will be displayed:

▼ Mount drive so data can be shared with client. (Do every time)

To run the following block of code. Hover your mouse over it and then click the play icon on the left of it.

Note: This may take you to another page where you need to authenticate with your google account.

If you find it takes ages (over three minutes) without doing anything then click the stop icon and then play again.

```
4m ✓ ▶ from google.colab import drive
drive.mount('/content/drive')
Mounted at /content/drive
```

STEP 3: Download RootPainter.

- Press the **play** button to run the code.

↳ Clone RootPainter repository (First time only, or if you need to update to the latest version)

This is done in order to download the source code into google drive so we can run the server application.

```
import os
assert os.path.isdir('/content/drive/MyDrive'), 'Are you sure the drive is mounted? See Mount drive step above'
!rm -r /content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src
!pip install imagecodecs # this is required to enable support for certain types of compressed tif images.
!git clone https://github.com/Abe404/rootPainter.git /content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src
```

Once the code has finished running the green tick and following messages are displayed:

↳ Clone RootPainter repository (First time only, or if you need to update to the latest version)

This is done in order to download the source code into google drive so we can run the server application.

```
import os
assert os.path.isdir('/content/drive/MyDrive'), 'Are you sure the drive is mounted? See Mount drive step above'
!rm -r /content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src
!pip install imagecodecs # this is required to enable support for certain types of compressed tif images.
!git clone https://github.com/Abe404/rootPainter.git /content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src
```

```
rm: cannot remove '/content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src': No such file or directory
Looking in indexes: https://pypi.org/simple, https://us-python.pkg.dev/colab-wheels/public/simple/
Collecting imagecodecs
  Downloading imagecodecs-2023.3.16-cp39-cp39-manylinux_2_17_x86_64_manylinux2014_x86_64.whl (36.1 MB)
    36.1/36.1 MB 33.6 MB/s eta 0:00:00
Requirement already satisfied: numpy in /usr/local/lib/python3.9/dist-packages (from imagecodecs) (1.22.4)
Installing collected packages: imagecodecs
Successfully installed imagecodecs-2023.3.16
Cloning into '/content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src'...
remote: Enumerating objects: 4040, done.
remote: Counting objects: 100% (1328/1328), done.
remote: Compressing objects: 100% (388/388), done.
remote: Total 4040 (delta 1028), reused 1176 (delta 936), pack-reused 2712
Receiving objects: 100% (4040/4040), 1.39 MiB | 9.47 MiB/s, done.
Resolving deltas: 100% (2476/2476), done.
```

This results in a new folder, '**rootPainter_src**' in your GoogleDrive, containing files needed to run RootPainter.

- **Do not** run the next section of code. It downloads a practise dataset for soil annotations that is not necessary for this workshop.

```

▼ Prepare biopores dataset (for testing the setup worked, first time only)

[ ] import os
  assert os.path.isdir('/content/drive/MyDrive'), 'Are you sure the drive is mounted? See Mount drive step above'
  !mkdir /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync
  !mkdir /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync/datasets

[ ] !wget https://zenodo.org/record/3754046/files/biopores_750_training.zip
  !unzip biopores_750_training.zip

[ ] import os
  assert os.path.isdir('/content/drive/MyDrive'), 'Are you sure the drive is mounted? See Mount drive step above'
  !mv biopores_750_training /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync/datasets/

```

- Start the server by pressing **play**. Note: unlike other sections of code, the server code does not 'complete' and show a tick next to it when its current action has finished. It is supposed to keep running until the user stops it.

▼ Start server (Do every time)

Note This cell should keep running until you stop it. Which you can do after you have finished using RootPainter.

```

▶ import os
  assert os.path.isdir('/content/drive/MyDrive'), 'Are you sure the drive is mounted? See Mount drive step above'
  !python /content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src/trainer/main.py --syncdir '/content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync'

```

Troubleshooting 1: If running the code above gives the output "can't open file [.] main.py" then you probably need to mount google drive. Go back to the instruction *Mount drive so data can be shared with client. (Do every time)*

Troubleshooting 2: If starting the server stopped working for you then you may need to run the 'Clone RootPainter repository' above as the code now receives the syncdir as a command line argument but you will need to update to the latest version (by running the clone command) for this to work.

Troubleshooting 3: If it appears the client is very slow it may be that other files are still syncing. On mac and windows you can inspect the google drive sync activity. It may be that client server interaction is interrupted by large amounts of sync activity from newly added datasets or other files you have in google drive.

Troubleshooting 4: See further advice in the FAQ if you run into trouble:
<https://github.com/Abe404/rootPainter/blob/master/docs/FAQ.md#question--why-is-the-segmentation-not-loading>

Once the server is running, the following will be displayed:

▼ Start server (Do every time)

Note This cell should keep running until you stop it. Which you can do after you have finished using RootPainter.

```

▶ import os
  assert os.path.isdir('/content/drive/MyDrive'), 'Are you sure the drive is mounted? See Mount drive step above'
  !python /content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src/trainer/main.py --syncdir '/content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync'

```

```

Creating /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync
Creating /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync/projects
Creating /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync/datasets
Creating /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync/instructions
2 workers assigned for data loader
GPU Available True
Batch size 4
Started main loop. Checking for instructions in /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync/instructions

```

This will have created a second new folder in your GoogleDrive. This is where your datasets and projects will be saved to.

- **Do not** run the next section of code. It places restrictions on the algorithm that can increase training speeds but may reduce accuracy. This can be tried as an alternative server if your dataset is simple.

▼ Experimental alternative: Start Server with restricted patch size.

This server will run faster (good for demos) but may result in models with slightly reduced accuracy.

Note This cell should keep running until you stop it. Which you can do after you are finished using RootPainter.

```
[ ] import os
assert os.path.isdir('/content/drive/MyDrive'), 'Are you sure the drive is mounted? See Mount drive step above'
!python /content/drive/MyDrive/rootPainter_src/trainer/main.py --syncdir /content/drive/MyDrive/drive_rp_sync' --patchsize 188
```

As this workshop does not utilise the 'biopores dataset', the next section of the GoogleColab notebook is also not relevant:

The biopores folder should also be synced to your local computer where you will run the client:

The 'Client set-up' section will download the RootPainter interface on to your device. This will be used to send commands to the GoogleColab notebook and will be the application through which you complete training.

- Either click the 'client releases' link within the GoogleColab notebook or follow it [here](#).

▼ Client setup

Find the latest release at the following link and download and run the appropriate installer (depending on your specific operating system) to install the RootPainter client (First time only)

[Client Releases](#)

After downloading it click on the downloaded file and run the client installer (First time only).

Troubleshooting 1: If you can't open the OSX application and receive the error message that the app may be damaged. Running the following from terminal has been found to fix the problem.

```
xattr -d com.apple.quarantine /Applications/RootPainter.app
```

- This will take you to RootPainter's GitHub page. Scroll to the software release with the 'latest' tag. Note: this may have a different version number to that displayed in this tutorial.

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository page for Abe404/rootPainter. The 'Releases' tab is active, showing two releases. The top release is '0.2.26.pre' (Pre-release) from Feb 13. The bottom release is '0.2.25' (Latest) from Jan 30. The '0.2.25' release is highlighted with a red box. Below the releases, there is a section for 'Assets' with 6 items.

- Click the installation file suitable for your device.

The screenshot shows the 'Assets' section of the GitHub release page. It displays a list of 6 assets:

Asset Name	Size	Date
RootPainterInstaller_0.2.25_windows.exe	104 MB	Jan 30
RootPainter_0.2.25_OSX_Mac.pkg	92.9 MB	Jan 30
RootPainter_0.2.25_Ubuntu20.deb	93.2 MB	Jan 30
RootPainter_0.2.25_Ubuntu22.deb	100 MB	Jan 30
Source code (zip)		Jan 30
Source code (tar.gz)		Jan 30

- We recommend saving the installation file within your downloads folder. This can increase compliancy of the software with university regulations.

- Your device may display warning messages halting the download process. Selecting **'More info'** on the first pop-up will allow **'Run anyway'** to be selected on the second pop-up:

- The RootPainter set-up window will then appear. Select **'Next'**.

- Choose an installation location. Again, we would recommend your **'Downloads'** folder. Click **'Install'**.

- The installation process should not take more than a few minutes. Once completed, select **'Next'**.

- Ensure the **'Run RootPainter'** box is selected in the next pop-up before clicking **'Finish'**.

STEP 4: Specifying the sync directory.

It is **very important** that this step is completed correctly.

- When the RootPainter interface opens for the first time, the following pop-up will appear:

- File explorer will then open. Select the '**drive_rp_sync**' folder in your GoogleDrive to specify this as your sync directory.

The main RootPainter interface will then appear, and installation is complete!

1.4 Dataset Movement

Now RootPainter has been installed, the '**Primnoa_training**' dataset previously downloaded can be quickly moved to the correct folder:

1. Select the '**Primnoa_training**' folder within your GoogleDrive.
2. Select '**Move to**' from the top panel.
3. Select the '**datasets**' folder within '**drive_rp_sync**'.
4. Click '**Move**'.

2. MODEL DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Dataset Preparation

This section is **for information only**. The following steps have already been performed on the practise dataset provided for time saving purposes. However, when conducting your own future studies, it is useful to understand how pre-processing can assist the training process.

Smaller images increase training speeds for RootPainter and reduce the annotation time per image for users. We therefore recommend using the 'create dataset' function within RootPainter before creating a new project. The data provided in this workshop was prepared as follows:

STEP 1: Select 'Create dataset' from the RootPainter main menu.

STEP 2: Input parameters

- Input a relevant **dataset name**.
- The **source image directory** should be set to the folder containing images you want to train a model on. This folder **does not** have to be stored within GoogleDrive.
- As the *Primnoa* sp. dataset only consists of 155 images, '**All images**' are included when creating the training dataset.
- The **maximum tiles per image** describes how many cropped training images will be produced from each image in the source image directory. Inputting 2 means the training dataset will essentially double in size to 310 images.
- The **target width and height** determine the size of the cropped images produced when creating the dataset.

- Dataset creation typically requires < 1 minute. Once completed, a folder containing the new training dataset will appear within your 'GoogleDrive > My Drive > drive_rp_sync > datasets'.

Important note: consider the input parameters carefully when creating your own training dataset.

Images used in training with RootPainter must be a **minimum of 720x720 pixels**. This means that if your input images are not at least double this width, there will be overlap between training images. This is discouraged.

For example, the input *Primnoa* sp. images were 1440x888 pixels. Therefore, a tile size of 720x720 pixels will permit two non-overlapping images to be produced for each input image.

Whilst doubling the dataset size through image cropping will not increase the total information provided to the algorithm, it will enhance user annotations and increase the speed of training.

Finally, the input images selected for the 'create dataset' function do not need to be stored within GoogleDrive. However, if you wish to apply your final model to the original images, then they must first be uploaded to GoogleDrive.

2.2 Creating a Project

STEP 1: Select 'Create dataset' from the RootPainter main menu.

STEP 2: Input project data.

- Input the project name as '**Primnoa**'. Then click 'Specify image directory'.

- Specify the image directory as the '**Primnoa_training**' folder, found through GoogleDrive > drive_rp_sync > datasets.

- Ensure **'Random Weights'** is selected, as we are starting training from scratch. Then click **'Create project'**.

The project will then open and display an image from the training dataset. The image order is randomised on project creation so you will likely see a different image in your project than the one shown here.

2.2 Starting Training

This tutorial aims to guide you through development of a model to identify and predict the area of *Primnoa* sp. Example images of *Primnoa* sp. from the training dataset are given below. The varied appearance of the branching coral results from polyp extension/retraction and differential lighting conditions.

RootPainter learns via corrective annotation. This means the algorithm presents a **prediction** based on its current model, which the user then corrects through highlighting **foreground** and **background** that the algorithm has missed (false negatives and positives, respectively).

Foreground = species of interest (*Primnoa* sp.)

Background = everything else

There are some important rules to note before beginning annotation (these will make more sense during the training process):

- **Do not over-annotate the background.**
 - RootPainter will initially predict a large amount of background as your species of interest. It is important not to correctively annotate the entire background of the image to avoid overwhelming the network. RootPainter will quickly improve its background predictions with limited annotation of these areas.
- **Do not annotate far distant objects.**
 - Poorly lit species of interest in the far background will often confuse the model you are developing. These individuals are also commonly ignored in manual studies as they are too far from the remotely operated vehicle (ROV) lasers to be reliably scaled.
- **It is better to under-annotate at the edge of objects than to annotate the border between foreground/background.**
 - The edges of objects can be difficult to define, particularly when zoomed. This can be seen to be an issue for the top left of the *Primnoa* sp. individual here.
- **If you are not sure, leave it.**
 - This applies to both initial and corrective annotations. If the model is **predicting foreground** and you are uncertain as to whether it is correct, it is best to perform no annotations. Otherwise, you risk confusing the model and disrupting training; another and clearer opportunity will arise to correct the model if needed. Likewise, do not highlight **foreground** or **background** unless you are certain of its classification.

STEP 1: Annotation controls.

Annotations are performed by clicking on the relevant area of an image, using the brush tool in the correct colour. The size and colour of the brush, as well as the image size and display can all be controlled through the top toolbar within the RootPainter application.

Project Edit Options Brushes View Network Measurements Extras

However, we would recommend becoming comfortable with the keyboard shortcuts as this can greatly reduce annotation time:

- **Q** = red brush (**foreground**)
- **W** = green brush (**background**)
- **E** = eraser brush
- **Z** = undo
- **Ctrl & shift & Z** = redo
- **S** = show/hide segmentation (**model prediction**)
- **A** = show/hide annotation
- **I** = show/hide image
- Mouse **scroll** = zoom in/out
- **Shift** & mouse **scroll** = adjust brush size
- **Ctrl & click & drag** = move around zoomed in image
- **Ctrl & F** = fit image to view
- **Ctrl & A** = view image actual size
- **Ctrl & C** = view image in context (only if using create dataset function)

It is possible to change the colour of the **foreground** and **background** brushes, but we would not recommend doing this during the tutorial to prevent confusion.

STEP 2: The first two images.

The first two annotated images serve as the initial ‘training’ and ‘validation’ components of the model. It is therefore very important to provide the algorithm with clear examples of **foreground** and **background**. It is not necessary to annotate the full image but zoom in and adjust your brush size to avoid errors.

- Change the brush colour to **red** (press Q) and highlight clear examples of ***Primnoa sp.*** in your image.
- Change the brush colour to **green** (press W) and highlight several sections of **background** in your image.

You can see in the above image that the buttons at the bottom say '**Previous**' and '**Loading Segmentation...**'. RootPainter will display the loading segmentation message until a **segmentation** (prediction for each pixel in this image) is returned from the GoogleColab server. You cannot proceed until the segmentation and '**Save & Next**' button appears:

The light blue colouring covering the image is the **model prediction**, or **segmentation**. At the start of training, the algorithm has not received any information, input in the form of annotations. Model predictions at this stage will be 'untargeted' and appear poor. These will visibly improve as you train models.

Waiting for the **segmentation** to be generated and synced can take a while. If the '**Loading Segmentation..**' text never goes away, check that the 'Start server (Do every time)' section of the GoogleColab webpage is running.

- Once the **segmentation** for your first image has loaded, and you have completed **foreground** and **background** annotations, click **'Save & Next'**.

RootPainter will then present a new random image from the training dataset. Repeat the same annotation process for your second image:

- Change the brush colour to **red** (press Q) and highlight clear examples of ***Primnoa sp.*** in your image.
- Change the brush colour to **green** (press W) and highlight several sections of **background** in your image.

- Once the **segmentation** has loaded click **'Save & Next'**.

Instructions and outputs during training are continuously listed on the **GoogleColab webpage**, under the server section. The following image shows what you should see in the server output after annotation of your first two images:

As previously mentioned, these first two images form the initial ‘training’ and ‘validation’ components of the model. You should be able to see your first two annotations assigned to these folders within your **GoogleDrive > drive_rp_sync > projects > Primnoa > annotations**. The model is now ready to begin training.

STEP 3: Starting training and annotating images 3-7.

- Under the ‘**Network**’ tab of the main RootPainter toolbar, click ‘**Start training**’.

This instruction should be reflected in the GoogleColab server display after a few seconds:

Then continue with annotations, in the same way as for images 1 and 2:

- Change the brush colour to **red** (press Q) and highlight clear examples of *Primnoa sp.* in your image.
- Change the brush colour to **green** (press W) and highlight several sections of **background** in your image.

Once training has started, the message **'Training 0 of max 60 epochs without progress'** will be displayed under your training images.

This number may increase and reset several times during training. It is not something to concern yourself with at this stage, but more information is provided in the 'Finishing training' section if you are interested at this time.

- Repeat annotations in this way until the **8th image** is reached.

At this point you should check the models folder under your Primnoa project: **'GoogleDrive > drive_rp_sync > projects > Primnoa > models'**

New and improved models are continually produced during training and will be output here. The first model contains the 'random weights' used to initialise the algorithm. The second and subsequent models are the result of training the algorithm on your annotated data. At least two models must exist in this folder before proceeding to STEP 4. As GoogleColab can be slow, you may need to wait a little as it can take 3-5 minutes for the next model to appear (after clicking start training).

STEP 4: Moving to corrective annotation.

Now the algorithm is learning and producing new models, you should also be seeing improvement in **segmentations (predictions)** by RootPainter.

It is therefore time to move to corrective annotations. This means you need to correct the **segmentations** provided for each image, rather than highlighting examples of **foreground** and **background** as with images 1-7. The algorithm will assume that any **segmentation** you do not highlight is correct. If you are unsure whether the **segmentation** is correct, it is best to leave it un-highlighted. You will have plenty of chance to refine the model later and we should avoid adding labels if we aren't certain, especially early in the training process. It is often useful to toggle the image display (press I) to see **segmentations** hidden in complex backgrounds.

- Change the brush colour to **red** (press Q) and highlight any **Primnoa sp.** that the algorithm has missed in its prediction in your image (these pixels are false negatives).
- Change the brush colour to **green** (press W) and highlight any **segmentation** that is not **Primnoa sp.** in your image (these pixels are false positives).

You should continue to annotate images in this way until the model is sufficiently trained (see **'2.4 Stopping Training'**).

The accuracy of the models increases as you annotate more images, therefore successive images require less time to annotate as you progress through the training dataset. Waiting for **segmentations** to load can hinder this progress. Therefore, once the ~7th image is reached, we would recommend using the 'pre-segment' function in RootPainter. This applies the current model to the subsequent 'x' number of images that will appear in training, meaning their **segmentations** are displayed instantly when said image is reached in training.

- Under the 'Options' tab of the main RootPainter toolbar, click 'Pre-Segment'.

- Change the value to '4' and click 'Okay'. It is not advised to increase this number to >10 as it may hinder model improvement.

Projects can be closed without causing a loss of data. If you want to continue training your model another day:

1. Re-mount your GoogleDrive and start the server in [GoogleColab](https://colab.research.google.com/).
2. Open the RootPainter application and select 'Open existing project'.
3. Select the **.seg_proj** file within your desired project folder
4. Select 'Network' > 'Start training' and then continue with corrective annotations.

2.4 Stopping Training

Qualitative model assessment

The continuous feedback loop created between the user and algorithm during training is unique in allowing qualitative assessment of when a model is sufficiently trained. In other words, when successive RootPainter predictions provided to you during training require minimal corrective annotation, you can assume your model is fit for purpose. That said, this decision making is subjective, and the number of successful successive predictions required before terminating training should be considered in relation to how varied the dataset is. For a dataset containing images with varying e.g. light properties or background objects more stringent stopping criteria may be needed.

Quantitative model assessment

The success of machine learning models is often quantified using metrics such as precision, recall, dice score and accuracy. They are calculated depending on true/false positives/negatives within a [prediction](#), with their values ranging from 0-1 where 1 is the best. These metrics are typically calculated by comparing a selection of the output [segmentations](#) of a model with manual annotations of the same input image (this is also known as model validation). The manually annotated images are taken as the 'true' areas, and the accuracy of the automated [segmentations](#) is then assessed based on classification of each pixel of the [segmentation](#) as a true/false positive/negative.

The corrective annotation process in RootPainter means these metrics can actually be calculated during training. For each training image users provide 'true' areas as a result of their corrective annotations. These fill the same purpose as the manual annotations discussed above. Corrective annotations can therefore be used to classify true/false positives/negatives for each training image, allowing continuous calculation of precision, recall, dice score and accuracy. Visualisation of how these metrics change during training can provide guidance to users for when to stop.

STEP 1: Select 'Extras' > 'Show metrics plot'

STEP 2: Move through the different metric plots to assess model progress.

STEP 3: Click on a data point to view its image and training annotations. This may help to explain why some values are so low.

Note that for the example below the dice score is poor, but the corrections for its respective image are minimal. Metrics can sometimes be misleading and we recommend that decisions to stop training should be both qualitatively and quantitatively informed.

The full complement of training metrics available within RootPainter can also be exported to a csv file by clicking 'Extras' > 'Export metrics CSV'.

3. MODEL APPLICATION

3.1 Segmenting a Dataset

Once you are happy with your model, the next step is to apply it to your total dataset. Before doing this you must ensure your GoogleDrive is mounted and the server is running within the [GoogleColab](#) notebook.

STEP 1: In the RootPainter main menu select 'Network' > 'Segment folder'

STEP 2: Specify input and output folders and model file.

- Input directory = image dataset you want to apply the model to (must be saved in and synced with GoogleDrive).
- Output directory = folder the results will be saved in
- Model file = likely the most recent .pkl model file within the 'models' folder of your project.

Segmentation time will vary depending on the size of your input folder and your internet connection. A progress bar will appear whilst the model is running and a pop-up will inform you when it has finished.

Results are output as .png files containing the **segmentation** for each input image. This allows users to check for obvious anomalies or issues with the model.

3.2 Extracting Measurements

Area, perimeter, diameter, x,y coordinates and eccentricity can all be simultaneously extracted, for each discrete area, in each .png **segmentation** output produced in section 3.1.

STEP 1: In the RootPainter main menu select 'Measurements' > 'Extract region properties'.

STEP 2: Specify your input and output files

- Segmentation directory = file containing .png **segmentation** outputs from step 3.1
- Output csv = give a filename relating to your results

Measurement extraction should be almost instantaneous.

STEP 3: Open your output .csv file

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	file_name	x	y	diameter	area	perimeter	eccentricity	
2								
3	20200708_10-	474.619	99.19048	5.170883	21	15.89949	0.96047	
4								
5	20200708_10-	630.3333	271.3333	1.95441	3	3.414214	0.816497	
6								
7	20200708_10-	638.5625	277.3438	6.383076	32	23.27817	0.88618	
8								
9	20200708_10-	618.3333	276.5	2.763953	6	6.414214	0.870388	
10								
11	20200708_10-	599.2857	283.4286	5.170883	21	17.24264	0.941439	
12								
13	20200708_10-	621.8571	281.0714	4.222008	14	11.41421	0.81654	
14								
15	20200708_10-	506.2	283.8	2.523133	5	5.414214	0.938083	
16								
17	20200708_10-	619.3333	286.6667	1.95441	3	3.414214	0.816497	
18								
19	20200708_10-	633.6667	287	1.95441	3	1.207107	0.973723	
20								
21	20200708_10-	638	286.5	2.256758	4	4.414214	0.924176	

There are some important things to note about results obtained with RootPainter:

- Measurements are given in **pixels**.
- **Multiple measurements will be given per image** as each discrete area within an image is processed separately.
- **If an image contains no segmentation, then it will not appear in the output .csv.** For example, you will not find a filename and corresponding area = 0 in your .csv.
 - As zero results are important, we would suggest making a file list of your input images and then merging this with the output list by filename.
- **Even the best models will produce segmentations containing artefacts.**
 - During corrective annotation there will be many <10 pixel segmentations missed by users. These very small errors are difficult to eradicate from a model. Instead, we would suggest ordering your results by area and excluding areas <10 pixels. However, this is just a guide and users should thoroughly consider the pixel dimensions of their images and the relative size of your subject of interest before deleting large volumes of data.

MODEL SHARING

One of the most exciting features of RootPainter is the ability to share models. In order to demonstrate this, a pre-developed model for *Primnoa* sp. is available within the workshop folder: [Image Analysis Made Easy](#).

Once the .pkl file is saved within your GoogleDrive, you can:

1. Directly apply the model to an image dataset

- a. Within the RootPainter main menu select '**Network**' > '**Segment folder**' and choose the new download as your model file

2. Continue training the model

- a. Within the RootPainter main menu select 'Create new project' and instead of random weights select 'Specify model'. This is really useful if you want to optimise a pre-developed model for a given species to a different dataset.

The screenshot shows the 'RootPainter' application window. It contains a 'Project name' text input field. Below it, the 'Image directory' is 'Not yet specified' with a 'Specify image directory' button. There are two radio buttons: 'Random Weights' (unselected) and 'Specify Model' (selected). Below the radio buttons, the text 'Model: Please specify model file' is displayed above a 'Specify model file' button, which is highlighted with a red rectangular border. At the bottom, there is a 'Name must be specified to create project' message and a 'Create project' button.

A platform to facilitate sharing of marine species models is currently under development.

CITATION

If you have found this handbook helpful and have used the information to guide your RootPainter study, please ensure to cite its zenodo DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7984565](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7984565)

The original RootPainter paper and the initial paper describing application of RootPainter to marine images should also be included in any research outputs:

[RootPainter: deep learning segmentation of biological images with corrective annotation](#).

[New Interactive Machine Learning Tool for Marine Image Analysis](#)